

PROSPECTS OF INTERNET IN LEARNING AND FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

In the educational process, the importance of consistency and reflection increases against the background of a decrease in the emotionality of communication. Internet technologies have an impact on the personality of the learner / student. At the same time, both extreme forms indicating a negative personality change (for example, Internet addiction and social isolation of a person) are possible, as well as positive personality changes due to communicative and cognitive activities on the Internet.

In the field of communication as humanity has experienced several stages of revolutionary change: the emergence of language - the emergence of writing - the printing press - the emergence of electronic media. At the same time, the last to date "fourth communicative revolution" [6, p.92] is taking place almost before our eyes. Through the widespread distribution of television, and then electronic (computer, telecommunication, Internet) technologies, a modern person clearly traces the transition from linear thinking to global perception, hypertext thinking is actively developing.

There are a wide variety of classifications of how the computer and the Internet can be used in the educational process. One of the most complete classifications today can be considered those that were proposed in her works by prof. E.S. Polat [2]. We will only discuss those areas that we will consider on the pages of this monograph:

- the Internet as a means of delivering information, including educational;

- the Internet as a learning environment;
- the Internet as a basis for the course of study (Internet textbook);
- the Internet as a source of didactic and teaching materials for their further processing or processing by the teacher;
- the Internet as a communicative environment for the formation and development of basic speech skills and communicative competence.

The attractiveness of Internet technologies is also due to the fact that they create an environment conducive to the development of the creative abilities of pupils and students by stimulating curiosity, non-regulation and multivariate learning, the formation and development of divergent (non-stereotypical) thinking, which is characterized by the ability to put forward many correct ideas at the same time by speed, flexibility, originality, and accuracy [1].

Learning, being a constructive process, is presented as one's own interaction with the world. Some of the characteristics that a student / student should possess seems

to be unrealistic. Such a student must be highly conscious and constantly motivated, have a comprehensive understanding of the learning process, which is not the sphere of his future professional competence. Most authors highlight the following main characteristics of the autonomous student. Autonomous student / learner:

- has an idea of the educational process, teaching methods and strategies;
- takes an active position in the learning process;
- takes risks in the learning process (risks include communication in a foreign language, associated with overcoming psychological barriers, etc.);
- develops a tolerant attitude towards the studied foreign language;
- takes responsibility for their own participation in the educational process;
- determines the goals and objectives of their own learning;
- has motivation in learning a foreign language and develops this motivation;

- draws attention equally to the form and content of the learning process;

- creates for its own purposes a reference system of the target language, regularly analyzing and revising the knowledge he has, generalizing and refining them.

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Information and communication technologies, which include the Internet, in education are associated with a number of socio-cultural factors that can positively or negatively affect the availability and use of Internet technologies. A number of studies examine inequality of opportunities and problems of access to education through information and communication technologies for a number of social groups, primarily those with low social status, which creates certain barriers to the effective use of Internet technologies in this area.

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